

METHODS USED IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO STUDENTS.

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ABSTRACT

In the article, there is an innovation of the English language teacher of general secondary schools ways to improve the quality of education through the use of methods are highlighted.

INTRODUCTION

Implementation of the developed experiences of pedagogy and achievements in education is one of the important conditions of today. Currently, a huge base of experiences that a teacher can use during his career has been formed, and it is getting richer every day. But despite this, it is difficult for teachers and future professionals to master these experiences [1-4]. The position of the teacher is especially important in creating best practices and popularizing them among colleagues. The educator should pay attention to the cost and effectiveness of the new advanced pedagogical practice. The orientation of the teacher's practical activity towards innovation is the implementation of the achievements achieved as a result of theoretical pedagogical research enables implementation. In order to popularize the results of such studies, it is necessary to introduce them to the general public. Such news can be conveyed to representatives of other pedagogies by providing quick advice, holding special seminars and trainings, giving speeches at conferences, and giving future pedagogues a series of lectures [5-9].

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

At this point, a question arises: "Who are the communicators and promoters of advanced pedagogical ideas and technologies to the general public?" Studying the experience of a particular pedagogue or educational institution, higher education in popularization professors and teachers of educational institutions, mature pedagogues working in universities play an important role in this process. The reason for this can be explained as follows:

- the author of the innovation cannot give a necessary and accurate assessment of the prospect of a particular pedagogical idea or innovation;
- advanced pedagogues are always about popularizing their ideas

they don't think. The reason is that innovation requires additional time and labor of the pedagogue;

- the idea is not always scientifically and methodologically justified by its creator;
- the authors face obstacles related to the individual characteristics of themselves and their colleagues when describing their innovations and ways of implementing them;
- the task of not only promoting and popularizing pedagogical innovations, but also making corrections to the quality of pedagogues based on them and enriching the professional knowledge and skills of future teachers is assigned to the creative group;
- systematic selection of innovations, monitoring, innovative idea.

The author of the innovative idea is an activity aimed at practical application does not participate in management [10-14]. This kind of approach creates a basis for expanding the capabilities of an innovative pedagogue and directing him to a specific goal.

In this way, the powers of the founder and popularizer of innovative pedagogy are concentrated in one point and directed towards a certain goal. Pedagogical innovations have their own dimensions. Pedagogical innovation consists of the following dimensions that shape the creative activity of a future teacher: how new the innovative methods are; its optimality; how effective; the possibility of using it in mass experiments and so on. The main measure of innovative methods is their novelty, results of scientific research and equality with advanced pedagogical experiences. For this reason, what is the real essence of innovation for teachers who want to work in the innovative process it is important to understand [15-17].

DISCUSSION

The experiment may be new to one teacher, but not new to another. In addition, the level of innovation of the same method may be different for future pedagogues. Taking this into account, both future pedagogues and teachers working in the educational system, based on their need for innovative creative activity should be approached. According to the degree of novelty, innovative methods that help to develop the creative functions of future pedagogues are manifested in several forms: absolute degree; local-absolute degree; conditional degree; subjective level. The mass application of innovative pedagogical innovations is interpreted as a criterion for their evaluation. This is mainly related to the technical support of the educational process and the uniqueness of the teacher's activity [18].

The creative application of pedagogical innovations in mass pedagogical experiments is manifested at the initial stage of the work of individual teachers. These innovations are offered for public use after being tested and objectively evaluated [19]. It is desirable to develop the creative functions of future teachers using innovative methods that are widely popular and allow to achieve positive results. Diagnostic methods aimed at studying the innovative activity of the teacher are also diverse. The use of diagnostic methods shows the strengths of the teacher's activity [20]. Therefore, equipping future teachers with modern methods of diagnosis is the demand of the times. Taking into account the professional needs and desires of future teachers. They form a professional-pedagogical ethics work and continuous it is necessary to carry out full-fledged targeted activities aimed at development.

THE RESULT

When studying pedagogical innovations on the basis of diagnosis, one should not forget the need to take into account the presence of positive, developing situations as well as negative manifestations in the experience of each pedagogue. In order for a young pedagogue to work

effectively in an educational institution, it is necessary to clearly demonstrate the positive and negative aspects of his work experience on the basis of diagnosis. It is necessary to clearly convey to future teachers that the methods of diagnosis used in order to study innovative processes are as follows.

- pedagogical needs, interests of future teachers, separately systematic study of important areas, identifying the difficulties encountered in teachers' activities and the possibilities of their elimination;
- ideas that serve to satisfy their interests and needs, search for concepts and advanced pedagogical experiences and introduce them into the practice of higher pedagogical education;
- to determine the originality of future teachers in the process of mastering and applying pedagogical innovations and their various manifestations, in which to demonstrate, describe, hold open classes, work on new resources, such as organizing lectures, participation in experimental work, and wide use of types of work. To study pedagogical innovations on the basis of diagnosis it is recommended to carry out directed practical work in several stages.

At the initial stage, questionnaire requests from future teachers, examination of answers to questionnaire questions, organization of individual interviews and confirmation of information in answers to questionnaire questions, analysis of information obtained based on the results of diagnosis [21]. At this stage, based on the results of the first stage, activities aimed at improving the professional and pedagogical qualifications of the future teacher will be planned and the ways of their implementation will be shown. At this stage, the work carried out is completed and repeated diagnosis is carried out. In this process, the future teacher is directed to obtain intermediate and final results. Changes in the activity of students in the group are analyzed in depth. As a result, diagnosing the professional skills, qualifications and experiences of future teachers and arming them with diagnostic methods, as well as restructuring the process of professional pedagogical education based on innovative ideas, will enable the effective development of students' creative activity.

As a result, future teachers are encouraged to be creative, there is an opportunity to encourage initiative [22]. The creative pedagogical activity of the teacher is the process of positively solving tasks subordinated to the formation of human consciousness and behavior, and most importantly, the creation of a generation of well-rounded people. Also, the planned educational goal is easily realized and the expected result will be achieved faster. That is;

- the role and tasks of the teacher in the system of innovative educational technology are clear must be determined;
- teacher new professional position - "teacher-technologist", - "pedagogue-technologist" should be raised to the level;
- "teacher-technologist" must have special knowledge, skills, qualifications;
- it is necessary to take specific measures to ensure the prestige, potential increase, spiritual and material interests of the "teacher-technologist" among the pedagogical team.

In order to improve the quality of education, the use of innovative technologies by teachers in the course of the lesson will definitely give effective results.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, in order to educate mature specialists who have a high level of general professional culture, social activity, independent thinking, and the ability to solve their tasks

without difficulty, today our pedagogues use modern and innovative pedagogical technologies. - they should understand that it is the main factor to improve the quality and efficiency of education, and that it is required by the times.

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